

TRANSMITTING POPULAR CULTURE TO FUTURE GENERATIONS THROUGH MARKETING: THE CASE OF THE GUARDIANS OF THE GALAXY FRANCHISE

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ABSTRACT

This study examines the strategies and approaches used to transmit popular culture to future generations through the implementation of various marketing techniques. Drawing on the example of Marvel Studios' "Guardians of the Galaxy" film franchise, the study analyzes the impact and significance of marketing strategies in the transmission process of popular culture. In order for popular culture to reach large audiences and maintain its influence in the long run, an effective marketing strategy is required. Product placement enables brands to interact with audiences in an organic manner by becoming a part of the storytelling process.

This paper examines the utilization of product placement, buzz marketing, and retro (nostalgic) marketing in transmitting popular culture to future generations, using the Guardians of the Galaxy franchise as a case study. By analyzing the marketing elements within the trilogy, including the three films and the existing literature on their marketing strategies, the objective of this study is to assess the efficacy of these marketing strategies when targeting Generation Z. This approach also stimulates interest in brands' future products, ultimately fostering long-term customer loyalty. Moreover, the paper addresses the delicate balance between marketing and entertainment. In an environment where viewers primarily seek entertainment, product placement needs to be seamlessly integrated into the narrative in a natural and organic manner. Lastly, the study underscores the role of the internet and social media in the transmission of popular culture to future generations. The "Guardians of the Galaxy" film franchise establishes a strong presence on social media platforms, facilitating interaction with viewers and enhancing brand reach. It has also been observed that the elements used to transmit this popular culture to future generations have transformed into internet memes and enhanced their marketing strategies.

Keywords: Popular Culture, Social Media, Internet Memes, Product Placement, Buzz Marketing

INTRODUCTION

Objectives of the Research

This study aims to examine the influence and importance of marketing strategies in the dissemination of popular culture. It seeks to assess the efficacy of these marketing approaches specifically when directed at Generation Z.

The research aims to comprehend the role played by the internet and social media in propagating popular culture to upcoming generations. The investigation delves into the conversion of

elements utilized for transmitting popular culture into internet memes and investigates their effects on marketing strategies.

Literature Review

A thorough examination of the available literature encompassing various topics such as popular culture, product placement, buzz marketing, and retro marketing, as well as the influence of the internet and social media on brand visibility and audience involvement, was carried out. This literature review served as the theoretical basis for the research, enabling the identification of existing knowledge gaps.

Figure 1: Guardians of the Galaxy Characters (First row from left to right: Yondu, Mantis, Peter Quill a.k.a. Star-Lord, Drax, Nebula; Second row from left to right: Cosmo, Groot, Rocket and Gamora)

Analysis of Movies; Guardians of the Galaxy: A Popular Culture Phenomenon

"Guardians of the Galaxy" is a film franchise adapted from the Marvel Comics' comic book series of the same name [1]. The first film was released in 2014 and achieved great success. The series (They have 3 of them till the date) offers a unique experience that combines music, adventure, humor, and visual effects. The main characters, Star-Lord, Gamora, Drax, Rocket, and Groot, have carved a special place in the hearts of the audience.

The three films from the "Guardians of the Galaxy" franchise were subjected to detailed analysis. This analysis aimed to identify instances of product placement, buzz marketing, and retro marketing within the films. By examining the specific techniques and strategies employed, the study sought to understand how popular culture was transmitted to the audience through these marketing elements.

Product Placement and Usage of ‘Guardians of Galaxy’

Product placement is a marketing technique where branded products or services are strategically incorporated or featured within the context of popular media, such as films, television shows, or music videos. It aims to subtly promote or expose the products to the audience, leveraging

the power of storytelling and visual exposure to enhance brand visibility, recognition, and association [2].

Figure 2: The Walkman TPS-L2

At first Star-Lord was using a 70's Walkman because he separated from his mother around that time, but in the 3rd movie they changed that bit for giving the Microsoft Zune as a return reputation. The Walkman TPS-L2 went on sale July 1, 1979, in Japan and in June the following year in the U.S. It retailed for a whopping \$200 [3]. Microsoft see this as an opportunity and tried to revitalize the Zune at the vol.3 and the price ranges from 70 to 500 dollar on Ebay now [4].

Figure 3 and 4: The Walkman at the first movie, Vol.1 and Microsoft Zune at Vol.3 shown as Star-Lord's belongings

Star-Lord's Playlist and The Buzz Marketing

Buzz Marketing is a marketing strategy that aims to generate popularity, curiosity, and conversation among the target audience for a product, service, or event by using fictional or real events. It is designed to create excitement, encourage sharing, and organically generate discussions about a brand or product. [5]

In "Guardians of the Galaxy," the utilization of various marketing strategies created a buzz among viewers. Including humorous dialogues and interactions between characters, elicited laughter and generated further discourse. These scenes, accompanied by effective marketing strategies, aimed to broaden the film's audience and cultivate a positive perception among viewers.

Figure 5: Awesome Mix Vol.1

The cassette, Star-Lord gets from his mother and keeps as a memory from her.

The music used throughout the film is also part of the Buzz Marketing strategy. The inclusion of popular songs in the movie attracted viewers' attention, leading to more discussions and debates about the film [6].

Although many songs in the film date back to the 80s, they were effectively utilized and won the affection of younger audiences. Here, we understand that major film production companies strive to keep their lucrative money-making machines active by relying on proven resources. In order to achieve this, they employ buzz marketing and other strategies.

Talking With the Gen Z by using Retro Marketing

Nostalgia marketing, also known as retro marketing, aims to evoke emotional connections with the past to capture consumer interest. It utilizes old songs, artists, and nostalgic elements to engage consumers and foster loyalty while introducing younger generations to cultural values [7].

To engage Generation Z through retro marketing, focus on authenticity, cultural relevance, personalization, social media presence, and influencer collaborations. By incorporating these strategies, you can effectively connect with Generation Z and leverage their interest in retro elements.

One relevant example is the enduring popularity of music groups like Modern Talking, which rose to fame in 1985 and held significant appeal to your mother during her youth. In the present context, Modern Talking's rekindled popularity can be attributed to several factors.

Firstly, the resurgence of nostalgia and the retro trend in contemporary culture have contributed to the renewed interest among younger generations in the music and culture of the 1980s [8].

Figure 6: “Modern Talking - You’re My Heart, You’re My Soul” Music Video from 1985

The widespread availability of digital platforms has facilitated the rediscovery and accessibility of Modern Talking's songs to today's audience. Social media platforms, with their potential for viral dissemination, have played a pivotal role in introducing the group to new audiences and revitalizing their fanbase. The group's success is also bolstered by innovative marketing strategies and rebranding efforts that successfully blend their nostalgic appeal with modern marketing techniques [9].

Modern Talking's captivating live performances continue to attract enthusiastic crowds and have contributed to sustaining their musical legacy. In conclusion, the enduring popularity of music groups like Modern Talking showcases the significance of effectively transmitting cultural heritage to younger generations through marketing initiatives, bridging the gap between different eras and preserving cultural identity within society.

It’s All Connected to Meme Marketing

Internet Memes; could be an image, video, piece of text, etc., typically humorous in nature, that is copied and spread rapidly by internet users, often with slight variations [10].

Meme marketing, when combined with retro strategies, effectively engages Generation Z. Memes, popular internet content, quickly spread and resonate with young audiences. By presenting nostalgia in a humorous and shareable manner, memes enhance retro marketing efforts. Leveraging Gen Z's social media presence, memes facilitate organic brand interactions and broader message dissemination [11]. Memes offer a shorter, contemporary, and impactful approach to connecting with Gen Z and reinforcing retro marketing.

Figure 7: I am Groot Meme

METHODOLOGY

This study utilizes a case study methodology, combining primary and secondary data sources, to analyze the marketing strategies employed in the Guardians of the Galaxy franchise. The case study will provide valuable insights into the effectiveness of these strategies in terms of brand awareness, audience engagement, and sales outcomes. Data collected from sources will provide a comprehensive understanding of the marketing techniques employed in the franchise and their impact on brand awareness, audience engagement, and sales.

FINDINGS

The findings of this study indicate the effectiveness of meme marketing strategies, product placement, retro marketing and buzz marketing in capturing the attention and interest of Generation Z within the Guardians of the Galaxy franchise.

The incorporation of nostalgic elements, references to 80s pop culture, and strategic product placements successfully increased brand visibility and recognition among viewers. Pre-release marketing campaigns generated excitement and engagement through social media activations and fan contests.

As a result of these efforts, the franchise experienced strong box office performance and merchandise sales, highlighting the significant impact of these marketing strategies on commercial success.

CONCLUSION

Theoretical Contributions

This study's theoretical conclusion emphasizes the contribution it makes to the existing literature on marketing techniques targeting Generation Z. It aims to pave the way for new understandings in the field by shedding light on effective marketing strategies like buzz, retro, and meme marketing. By highlighting the significance of incorporating nostalgic elements, strategic product placements, and engaging pre-release campaigns, this research demonstrates how marketers can capture the attention and sustain the interest of Generation Z. Overall, this theoretical conclusion emphasizes the study's academic value and its potential to advance the marketing field.

Managerial

The managerial conclusion of this study focuses on providing practical implications for marketers targeting Generation Z. Based on the findings, marketers should consider incorporating nostalgic elements, strategic product placements, and engaging pre-release campaigns to effectively engage Generation Z consumers. Buzz, retro, and meme marketing are identified as key strategies that can lead to commercial success when targeting this demographic. By implementing these insights, marketers can enhance their marketing efforts and achieve better results when engaging Generation Z. This managerial conclusion emphasizes the study's practical significance and actionable insights for marketing practitioners.

Contributions

Limitations

The limitations of this research should be taken into consideration. For instance, this study solely focused on marketing strategies targeting Generation Z, without conducting a comparative analysis with other demographic groups. The research scope was confined to specific marketing techniques, and there was no comparative investigation with different marketing methods. The findings of this study are based on marketing trends and consumer behaviors that may change over time due to temporal effects. Future research should incorporate long-term studies to track how marketing strategies and consumer preferences evolve over time. Future research could focus on these areas to compare marketing responses among diverse demographic groups and conduct a more comprehensive analysis. The data collection methods and analysis techniques employed in this study may also have limitations. Future research could contribute to validating the results by utilizing more extensive and diverse data collection methods. Moreover, implementing additional statistical analysis and quantitative research methods could strengthen the foundation of the conclusions.

Future Research

Future research could explore the impact of different types of nostalgic elements on Generation Z's engagement and brand loyalty, examine the applicability of retro marketing strategies in diverse industries and contexts, investigate the long-term effects of nostalgia-driven campaigns on brand perception and consumer behavior, and explore the role of social media influencers in amplifying the reach and impact of retro marketing efforts.

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